

DIAGNOSTIC OF URBAN FLOODING IN NAIROBI

Report 2024

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Organization: ITC-BMS, University of Twente

Delivered by: SPACE4ALL

Edited by: Lorraine Trento Oliveira

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**UNIVERSITY
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“Here, floods are a blessing and a curse”

Pauline Wegumo, Mathare leader, April 13th 2024.

Executive Summary

Under the changing climate conditions and El-Niño in rainy seasons, global reports projected devastating floods in Nairobi. Despite numerous reports and media coverage about the flood impacts on the residents, especially on the urban poor, spatial evidence (e.g., detailed flood modelling) at the city scale is absent.

This report aims to address this gap by presenting a comprehensive flood map for Nairobi. We highlight affected areas, and recommend preliminary measures for hazard mitigation and adaptation. The report is produced by the Space4All project. Space4All aims to map the hotspots of urban poor, vulnerable to flood hazards, using citizen science. In this light, we work together with local stakeholders, especially groups normally excluded. Our approach is fostering inclusion, knowledge production and awareness.

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1 Introduction

Kick-started in 2023, the Space4All project has worked closely with residents from four different slums, local authorities and NGOs to map flood hotspots in Nairobi. The team implemented and locally validated a state-of-the-art fast flood model, while incorporating local perspectives. The recent tragedies of the floods in April and May 2024 highlight the dramatic effects of urban floods and the pressing need for spatially explicit, locally relevant flood information.

Our results include the outputs of a flood model, a pilot open-source mapping tool, and a flood observation dataset mapped by community members. During fieldwork, the team also discussed vulnerability aspects and the direct and indirect impacts of floods on the life of the residents.

Project Context

Nairobi, the capital city of Kenya, is the largest city in the country, with approximately 4.4 million inhabitants (roughly 10% of the country's population). The city is marked by rapid urbanization and a complex spatial distribution, which impact the sustainable function of the drainage and sewage systems. On top of that, around 60% of people live in unplanned areas. Low-income areas often occupy the urban fringes, especially riparian zones or floodplains, facing extreme consequences. Poor drainage systems and reduced pervious surfaces increase flood risks. As a result, unplanned areas are often facing the highest death toll in the city. Kibera, Mathare, Mukuru and Kariobangi communities are known to be subject to flood impacts and are selected as focus areas of this project.

Even though it is known that floods disrupt the lives of most Nairobians during rainy seasons, the national government has been focusing their efforts on rural areas. Urban flood risk management remains constrained within local government bodies, and resources for addressing flood risks in unplanned settlements are scarce,

further challenging effective interventions in these high-risk areas.

The lack of spatial data is a constraint to effective flood mitigation and adaptation strategies. The existing flood hazard outputs for Nairobi mostly use terrain data, not accounting for precipitation and urban local factors. Models that do use such factors employ highly complex, computationally demanding simulation tools, hindering their scalability and usability for local actors.

Additionally, since no spatially explicit flood assessment has been done at the city scale, reference data for validation are lacking. Integrating local knowledge and citizen-generated data with global data and technologies can mobilize wider insights and support inclusivity (particularly of marginalized groups). Collaborative methodologies to support integrated and sustainable flood management in Nairobi are an essential principle of Space4All.

Project goals and contributions

Based on the aforementioned challenges, this project aims:

- I. To engage local stakeholders in the research process.
- II. To develop and test participatory data collection approaches.
- III. To map flood hazard extent and assess causing factors in Nairobi.

Understanding risk

The concept of risk plays a central role in flood assessments, particularly in the context of climate changes impacts. The IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report (AR6) defines disaster risk as the potential for adverse consequences on lives, livelihoods, ecosystems, and infrastructure due to climate-related hazards. Disaster risk arises from the interplay between three components: hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.

A hazard is defined as the physical event or phenomenon that could potentially cause harm. In the case of urban flooding in Nairobi, heavy rainfall, exacerbated by climate change, serves as a primary hazard. Exposure refers to the presence of people, assets, or ecosystems in areas that are subject to hazards. In Nairobi, formal and unplanned settlements located in flood-prone areas are especially exposed. Vulnerability is the predisposition of exposed elements to be adversely affected when impacted by hazards. Vulnerability is shaped by a range of factors, reflecting socio-economic, infrastructure and governance conditions that may exacerbate risks.

Measuring these concepts and analyzing their interaction with the human and environmental factors is not an easy task. It requires a lot of (spatial) information whose acquisition can also be challenge. In this report, we are focusing on the mapping hazard and exposure in Nairobi, assessing the size of the floods, identifying factors that can intensity their impacts and quantifying exposed groups.

2 Methodology

2.1. Stakeholders Engagement

Citizen science is the foundation of this project. This includes the involvement of residents in the scientific process. Our goal is to work with citizens as co-researchers, including different stakeholders and ensuring their information needs are fully incorporated into the project. This brings a wider range of people into the research, with benefits on diversity and inclusion, enhancing the understanding of the flood problem.

The first task, therefore, was to connect with a diverse of stakeholders and to learn how the project can support their information needs. From November 2023 and March 2024, online meetings were held with CommunityMappers (SDI-affiliated) members and with Nairobi City County representatives. The CommunityMappers are currently based in Kibera and act as a contact point for the other three local communities. They pled the need for localized flood maps, which should include safe spots/zones, urban infrastructure and facilities. The meetings were also used to codevelop a data collection approach.

Table 1 - Stakeholders involved in the project.

Stakeholder Category	Stakeholders Involved	Activities
International Institutions	Safer Nairobi Initiative (UN-Habitat)	Workshop
Government Agencies	Nairobi City County, Kenya Meteorological Department	Stakeholder Mapping, Workshop
Civil Society Institutions	Shack Dwellers International – Kenya	Workshop
Research Institutions	Technical University of Kenya APHRC	Data sessions, consultation, workshop
Community-based Organizations (CBOs)	CommunityMappers, Ghetto Foundation, Mathare Community Social Justice Centre	Data collection codesign, Training, Workshops, Transect walks

Table 1 summarizes the stakeholders involved in this project and engagement activities. The CBOs working at the community level provide information, connect to prospective workshop participants and field data collection. The other stakeholders acting at the city level participated in the validation workshop.

2.2. Local Data Collection – participatory approaches

The three primary data collection procedures during fieldwork in Nairobi were: local workshops, field surveys and transect walks. These procedures were applied to assess and optimize the flood model output, as well as foster dialogue and awareness about the local flood issues.

Firstly, between April 3rd and April 19th 2024, a series of **workshops** were conducted in Nairobi. One in each of the four selected communities and one at the city level.

In collaboration with Community Mappers, 10 participants were selected from each community, ensuring participant diversity concerning their age, gender, home location and community roles (e.g. Red Cross disaster risk responder). At the city level, 23 local experts attended, representing various institutions, including the City County Government, Shack Dwellers International (SDI), Technical University of Ghana, Safer Nairobi Initiative (UN-Habitat) and African Population and Health Research (APHRC).

The workshops were structured in three sessions: one focused on flood hazard model validation, the second on the flood factors and the third on the direct and indirect impacts¹. The first session was a group activity. Using marker pens, pins and sticky notes, the participants marked areas correctly assigned as (recurrently) flooded and areas that should be marked as flooded and were not. They pinpointed previous flood events on the map, describing impacts on the neighborhoods. The

¹ This session is part of the second stage of the Space4All project, vulnerability mapping, thus it won't be further explained in this report.

groups presented their results to the plenary and discussed validation procedures, indicating high agreement between them.

In the second session, the participants ranked the importance of flood factors in each area using a pair-wise voting technique. Based on literature, seven groups of factors were derived, including built-up (area, density and arrangement of buildings) and environmental factors (low-lying areas, green spaces, soil composition and waste disposal). The participants collectively voted for each pair of factors and discussed if agreement was not met until the entire pairwise matrix was completed. The final importance rank was derived from the sum of votes for each paired factor, i.e., the more votes, the more important to that specific location. The resulting matrices of the five workshops were used to analyze the flood model outputs.

For the second data collection procedure, Space4All co-developed with CommunityMappers a method to collect flood observation points using the Google My Maps application (see next page). After the user information meeting, two online testing and validation meetings were conducted. Considering limitations (technology and energy access) and data accountability, our co-researchers provided valuable input about storage and dissemination of the data and outputs.

On April 8th, the **training** was conducted with eight residents (two of each community). Printed maps were used for the recognition exercise. In this exercise, the participants got familiar with the spatial content of Google My Maps.

A tutorial was adapted from the Data4HumanRights² material. A survey was co-created in this session, including information on flood event dates, depth and damage. Additionally, the group was trained for the **field survey**.

Additionally, an online messaging group was set up to share information, address issues and provide feedback. The surveyed data is stored in My Maps files and later added to our model as flood depth measurements for calibration.

Thirdly, two **transect walks** with local stakeholders from Mukuru and Mathare communities contributed to the collection of quantitative flood information on April 12th. The two selected areas included two main rivers of the city that meet in the Nairobi River (Ngong and Mathare). The route was decided with community leaders and selected participants in each location. This selection was based on their in-depth knowledge (from activism and long-lasting dwelling), and availability. The goal was to explore the existing structures and conditions of the area. Following the map with a mobile device, the team observed (with photographs) flood depth markings, listened to the participants expressing their knowledge and identifying critical drainage areas.

² <https://www.data4humanrights.net/training-materials/5-2-google-maps-app>

TRANSECT WALKS APRIL 12, 2024

Mathare river

02

Mathare Park

Destruction of the riverbank structures

04

Ngumba

Market stalls always flooded

BH bridge

Observed flood height about 150cm

01

03

Mbili

Water markings above 1m

05

Whynot

Community center flooded up to 3m high

01

Gatoto Bridge

March 2024: 1st time that houses are swept there

Ngong river

St. E. School

Landslide and erosion

02

Lunga Lunga

Playground and houses swept away

03

Mathioya

Red Cross Markings (150 cm), bridge swept away, no access to school

04

2.3. Flood modelling

This section describes the methodology of the flood mapping process. As the first step, a historical inspection was conducted, to verify past flood events reported in online media sources. An extensive accuracy check through the respective years was conducted, websites were screened, and official documents were collected to confirm the exact dates, duration of flood events and reported impacts. It became clear that most cases and provided data are reported solely at the national level.

In the absence of flood information at city scale, the project drew upon a state-of-the-art flood model recently developed by the ITC Faculty researchers, FastFlood Simulation (FFS) method (see interface below).

This decision is based on (1) the fact that FFS uses an open source, user friendly web-based platform. This reduced the impact of software costs and increased the future replicability of the method by the local stakeholders; (2) the lower computational demands, when compared to traditional hydraulic models, allowing computation of large catchment areas in a few minutes.

The model requires input datasets representing rainfall events (duration and intensity), elevation, terrain roughness and infiltration. Aside from rainfall, all datasets were automatically downloaded from FFS inventory, using open globally available repository.

After simulations with each available dataset, the satellite-derived rainfall data was prioritized over open-access gauge measurements from the Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO)³. The institute provided daily and hourly precipitation data for three stations in Nairobi in a time series from January 2019 to January 2024. Among the three, the measurements of the Kenya Metrological Department (KMD) were the most comparable to the events reported on the Global Flood Monitor⁴. The 24-hour event on May 13th, 2021, was selected for the final simulation due to the highest peak rainfall of 62mm/h. The table below describes the selected datasets and the detailed documentation can be found on the official website⁵.

Input	Data	Source	Properties	Link
Climate factor	Rainfall	Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO)	Daily precipitation – no spatial resolution	https://tahmo.org/
Catchment properties	Terrain	Copernicus GLO-30 DEM	Resolution: 40m	Earth Engine Catalog
	Land use	Copernicus WorldCover	Resolution: 10m / 2021	ESA WorldCover 2021
	Infiltration	SOILGRIDS (ISRIC)	Resolution: 250m / 2020	SoilGrids — global gridded soil information ISRIC

After fieldwork, the flood observation points collected using Google My Maps and transect walk measurements were used to calibrate the model. The non-numeric flood depth information (ankle, knew, waist and above-the-head level) was converted into numeric thresholds and used to improve the accuracy of the model. Additionally, using the in-built calibration functions of FFS, infiltration and land use parameters were calibration the better reflect the reality on the ground.

The flood model outputs were evaluated qualitatively with the input from the workshops and quantitatively with two reference layers. After calibration, the results were validated using: (1) the satellite-derived flood extent from UNOSAT⁶ derived from very-high-resolution imagery for the recent flood events of May 2024; (2) the

³ <https://tahmo.org/>

⁴ [Global Flood Monitor](#)

⁵ [FastFlood | FastFlood website, free super-fast flood modelling tool.](#)

⁶ <https://unosat.org/products/3837>

flood map derived from the KDI project⁷ for the May 2021 floods. Lastly, flood exposure was mapped and assessed using the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) of 2023⁸. The overall methodology workflow is illustrated in detail below.

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2023.103499>

⁸ Global Human Settlement - Download - European Commission (copernicus.eu)

3 Key Findings

The results provide an overview of the flood patterns in Nairobi, with the estimated flood depth and extent for the event of May 13th, 2021. It is possible to see higher flood exposure in the eastern part of the city and along the major rivers. Areas of high exposure are often found in slums. This aligns with the results of the flood factors ranking exercise, where the residents acknowledged the construction near rivers as one of the major causes of flooding. The equally influencing factor is poor waste management, which leads to drainage blockage. The effects of lack of waste collection are very acute in unplanned areas. Furthermore, only a small portion of the resident’s houses are connected to the formal drainage system.

Workshop results - Ranking of Flood Causing Factors

At city scale, 27% of total area of Nairobi is flood prone. The levels of exposure considerably change depending on the presence (and layout) of built-up structures. When looking into the exposed elements, the denser an area is, the more likely are people and structures to be affected. The analysis shows that 35% of the total built-up areas of Nairobi are exposed to floods, of which 20% are densely built-up. Comparing formal and unplanned area, we found that 54% of formal areas exposed to floods are densely built-up against 99% of the unplanned ones. Considering the different levels of built-up in planned zones, 63% of the exposed cells are located in low built-up areas, mostly covering areas on the outskirts of the city.

At the sub-county level, Kasarani and Langata are the most susceptible areas, but a large part is non-built-up, thus transferring the titles to Embakasi South (27%) and Kamukunji (25%). In the first sub-county, the highly exposed built-up areas include the Mukuru area (including Viwandani, Kwa Jenga and Ruben settlements). In the latter, the highest exposure refers to the series of low-income areas in the boundaries of the National Air-Force base along the Nairobi River.

From the group of highly built-up areas, Embakasi Central (97%), Mathare (94%), and Starehe (87%) lead the flood exposure ranking. Each one of them is bounded by at least two of the three main rivers of the city, housing many low-income high-density areas. A similar situation is found in Kayole, Mathare and Mukuru Village.

We also inspected the areas that mostly low or not built-up. The inspection revealed that such areas are also exposed to floods in Embakasi East, covering slums (as Soweto and Mukuru Kwa Njenga) and formal residential areas along the Ngong River. The same is found in the Westlands along the Nairobi River, showing that both planned and unplanned structures are exposed to floods.

Mathare

Korogocho

Kibera

Mukuru

★ Landmarks Observed flood depth: ● Waist ● Knee ● Ankle

When we look closely at the four selected slum areas, the percentage of areas exposed to floods is: 16% (Kibera), 26% (Mathare), 36%(Mukuru), and 40% (Korogocho). The difference between built-up and non-built-up is insignificant since these settlements are very densely built-up. Yet, local validation procedures showed some important differences on the ground.

The first issue relates to high built-up growth that was not captured by the slum map, which might underestimate the size and number of settlements and, consequently, their flood exposure. Secondly, the results of the workshop validation and the My Maps field survey indicate that the flood model cannot capture the complexity of localized flooded areas. Again, this suggests that the flood exposure percentages from our model are likely higher on the ground.

An additional concern is that many local landmarks and facilities, such as schools and hospitals, are located close to or in the exposed zones. The testimonials of extreme flood depth (above 1.5 m) in the Whynot community center in Mathare, in the Undugu High Rise hospital in Kibera and in the Ruben Centre in Mukuru indicate a lack of safe spots for community evacuation. Considering the underestimation issue described above, more facilities are likely, like the Raila center in Kibera and the Vision playground in Mukuru, mentioned during the workshops.

Unmapped spots are often situated in the middle of the settlements with lower flood depths (less than 50cm high – smaller black dots on the maps), shedding light on the impacts of so-called artificial floods. These are caused by inappropriate waste disposal, obstructed drainage lines and the organic and dense building layout. In this context, the influence of the urban morphology and the lack of waste collection on flood susceptibility is clear.

In the transect walks, residents acknowledged that some constructions have been changing the river's natural path. On top of that, the sewage lines that are often not connected to the formal systems, the open sewer and provisional bridges are prone to overflow and destruction during rainy seasons. This suggests that the flood impacts would be massively reduced with higher investment in drainage and sanitation infrastructure.

4 Key Learnings

This report provides a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic planning to mitigate flood exposure in Nairobi and co-developed tools for advocacy in unplanned areas to plead for better disaster risk response and policies.

Space4All findings show that Nairobi is affected by flood events. The slum inhabitants of Nairobi are more exposed than the inhabitants of formal areas. The majority of the formal areas have low exposure, especially in the Eastern and Southwest parts of Nairobi, aside from areas along the riverways. The data and outputs confirm that the built-up characteristics of slums highly influence their flood susceptibility, which is stressed by both policymakers and community members. As natural water flows are impeded by houses, informal infrastructure and inadequate waste disposal, artificial floods increase the severity of impacts. Additionally, the high built-up density and low soil permeability also intensify the consequences on the historical natural swampy terrain.

This research provides an open-source, easy-to-use flood model, which is fundamental to mapping and quantifying flood exposure in the city. At the same time, the validation with the residents highlighted the severity of the reality on the ground, one the model does not account for the complex urban structures. Ideally, the inclusion of local discharge measurements and higher-resolution datasets would improve the applicability of the approach by the local agencies.

Overall, participatory data procedures are essential for localized models and understanding flood vulnerability. Involving the local communities has proven essential. Residents spotted the model inaccuracies, critically discussed the possible flood causes, observed their communities in detail, reflected on the power of the tools and used them for their own community projects too. The communities are aware of the problems of building in riparian zones and are interested in contributing to mitigation and prevention measures. We see local engagement as instrumental to any initiatives to support building the resilience of the communities. The lack of success or sustainability of past efforts is likely related to the ineffective involvement of slum residents in the process.

There are remaining challenges to be tackled in the methodology: (1) the data collectors using Google My Maps can only map flood points along riverbanks and streets, which introduces a bias for validation; (2) many areas could not be reached not measured during transect walks, mostly for physical and social barriers; (3) the methodology applied in this project works with an absence of discharge measurements. It is possible that the results would be different if the local discharge behaviors could be analyzed. This would require local data collection campaigns to determine the base discharge conditions.

Nevertheless, optimization of the techniques and the data employed are very welcome, especially considering the replicability of the methodology by the local institutions in other unplanned areas. In this sense, updated and enumeration maps of the slum areas would be of great importance for more accurate analysis and, most importantly, to include more communities on the process. The planning agencies should push integration of the slums to the formal urban fabric, including them into participatory mapping approaches and, consequently, in disaster risk policies.

Recommendations to Planning Agencies

Considering the intensification of disaster risk due to climate change, flood risk management must be integrated as a central part of urban development. In the context of slums, there is a lack of information and local engagement. The concept and the consequences of flood risk are context-specific, and involving the residents leads to learning the local perspective, co-creating strategies and synchronizing priorities. Urban projects need to ensure the engagement of community members for more sustainable and efficient strategies. This should push new efforts (and resources) to integrate the communities living in slums into disaster risk plans, including long-lasting planning structures. We propose the following recommendation guidelines to support integrated flood risk adaptation and mitigation in Nairobi.

Community Engagement

Support awareness campaigns on flood risks and preparedness measures.

Train community members in emergency response and increase government response.

Data and Models

Establish a comprehensive flood monitoring network, collaborating with community reporting and data collection systems.

Use the flood as entry point for engagement in formal and informal settlements.

Policy and Planning

Diagnose local flood vulnerabilities and codevelop strategies with the communities, including enumeration efforts.

Incorporate and develop the local drainage infrastructure to the existing formal systems.

Outlook

This project is specifically interested in the dissemination of the outputs to local stakeholders. There are many possibilities for knowledge transfer, including (1) the training of the institutional staff to work with FFS platform for rapid flood assessment; (2) further testing the model with local discharge measurements by the local authorities in collaboration with local community-based groups; (3) and the promotion of photo voice exhibition, supporting ongoing community awareness campaigns; (4) and outreach via media sources, such as the dissemination video attached to this document.

This report was written after the floods of May 2024 with many lives lost and devastating effects, reassuring the urgency for better information and disaster risk policy. In the next part of the research, our effort will focus on unraveling the relation between flood impacts and underlying local vulnerabilities. This analysis was already initiated during the local workshops by the codesign of the impact chains (mentioned earlier in this report). The project will continue to work with the local government and the local communities, offering support and collaborating for knowledge exchange and feedback.

5 Acknowledgements

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FINAL REPORT

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